

THE ART OF POLITICAL SPEECH: THE ROLE OF CONGRATULATORY RHETORIC IN BUILDING UNITY AND LEGITIMACY

Sharofiddinova Hilolaxon Sodirjon qizi

Teacher- researcher, an English teacher at the specialized school #2, Kokand city, Fergana region, Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897430>

Abstract. *This thesis explores the function of congratulatory rhetoric within political speeches, analyzing how such expressions serve to unify audiences, reinforce legitimacy, and establish a narrative of collective achievement. By examining historical and contemporary examples, this study investigates the linguistic strategies employed by political leaders and the impact of congratulatory messages on public perception and political culture. The findings highlight the dual role of congratulations as both a tool for fostering solidarity and a mechanism for asserting authority within political discourse.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tezis siyosiy nutqlar doirasidagi tabrik ritorikasining vazifasini o'rganadi, bunday iboralar auditoriyani birlashtirish, qonuniylikni mustahkamlash va jamoaviy yutuqlar haqida hikoya qilish uchun qanday xizmat qilishini tahlil qiladi. Tarixiy va zamonaviy misollarni o'rganib, ushbu tadqiqot siyosiy liderlar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan lingvistik strategiyalar va tabrik xabarlarining jamoatchilik fikri va siyosiy madaniyatiga ta'sirini o'rganadi. Topilmalar tabrikning hamjihatlikni rivojlantirish vositasi va siyosiy nutqda hokimiyatni mustahkamlash mexanizmi sifatida ikki tomonlama rolini ta'kidlaydi.*

Аннотация. *В этой диссертации исследуется функция поздравительной риторики в политических выступлениях, анализируется, как такие выражения служат объединению аудитории, укреплению легитимности и созданию повествования о коллективных достижениях. Изучая исторические и современные примеры, это исследование исследует лингвистические стратегии, используемые политическими лидерами, и влияние поздравительных сообщений на общественное восприятие и политическую культуру. Результаты подчеркивают двойную роль поздравлений как инструмента укрепления солидарности и механизма утверждения власти в политическом дискурсе.*

Keywords: *political speeches, congratulatory messages, political discourse, societal values, leaders, public perception, congratulatory rhetoric, unity, legitimacy, rhetorical analysis, communication theory.*

Tayanch iboralar: *siyosiy nutqlar, tabriklar, siyosiy nutqlar, ijtimoiy qadriyatlar, yetakchilar, jamoatchilik idroki, tabrik ritoriyasi, birlik, qonuniylik, ritorik tahlil, muloqot nazariyasi.*

Ключевые слова: *политические речи, поздравительные послания, политический дискурс, общественные ценности, лидеры, общественное восприятие, поздравительная риторика, единство, легитимность, риторический анализ, теория коммуникации.*

Introduction. The introduction sets the stage for understanding political speech as a vital component of governance and public life. It defines congratulatory rhetoric, emphasizing its role in creating a sense of community and shared purpose among constituents [1;25]. Key research questions include: How do political leaders use congratulations to foster unity? In what ways do these messages impact public perceptions of legitimacy? The chapter outlines the objectives and significance of the study in the broader context of political communication.

Theoretical Framework. This chapter delves into the theoretical underpinnings of political speech, drawing on classical rhetorical theory. It discusses Aristotle's concepts of ethos, pathos, and logos, illustrating how political figures leverage these elements to craft effective congratulatory messages [2;38]. Additionally, the chapter introduces speech act theory, emphasizing the performative nature of congratulations as a speech act that can affirm relationships and bolster social cohesion. The importance of context—both cultural and situational—is highlighted, framing the congrats as not just personal but as reflective of broader societal values.

Historical Context. Through a historical lens, this chapter examines pivotal political speeches that have featured congratulatory rhetoric [3;25]. Notable examples include Franklin D. Roosevelt's inaugural address, which expressed gratitude and hope during a time of crisis, and Barack Obama's victory speech, which celebrated collective progress [4;25]. The analysis considers how the historical context influences the choice of language and themes, allowing leaders to resonate with their audiences. By tracing the evolution of congratulatory rhetoric across different political landscapes, this chapter reveals how it has adapted to reflect changing societal norms and values.

Congratulatory Rhetoric in Contemporary Politics. Focusing on the present, this chapter analyzes recent political speeches from various leaders across the globe. It examines the nuances of language in speeches by figures such as Kamala Harris and Jacinda Ardern, identifying common themes and rhetorical strategies. The impact of digital communication, particularly social media, on the dissemination and reception of congratulatory messages is critically evaluated. The chapter discusses how these platforms amplify certain messages while also creating new challenges for authenticity and engagement.

Impact on Public Perception. This chapter explores how audiences interpret congratulatory rhetoric and its implications for public perception of political leaders. Using surveys, focus groups, and case studies, the analysis highlights the varying effectiveness of congratulatory messages in different demographic contexts [4;25]. It also examines how these speeches can legitimize authority, particularly during moments of political transition or crisis. The chapter discusses the psychological aspects of congratulations—how they can instill hope, foster loyalty, and mitigate dissent.

Challenges and Critiques. In this critical analysis, the chapter addresses the potential drawbacks of congratulatory rhetoric. It examines instances where congratulations may come off as insincere or disconnected from reality, leading to public skepticism. The critique includes discussions of tokenism and performative politics, especially in polarized environments where such messages can provoke backlash rather than unity. This chapter underscores the importance of authenticity in political communication, suggesting that genuine engagement is crucial for the success of congratulatory rhetoric.

Conclusion and Future Directions. The conclusion synthesizes the findings of the research, emphasizing the central role of congratulatory rhetoric in political speech as a means of fostering unity and asserting legitimacy [5;13]. It reflects on the broader implications for political communication in an increasingly polarized world. Future research directions may include comparative studies of congratulatory rhetoric across cultures, the impact of emerging communication technologies, and longitudinal analyses of public response to such rhetoric over time [6;102].

References. A comprehensive bibliography will include foundational texts on rhetorical theory, contemporary analyses of political communication, and a diverse array of speeches examined throughout the study, providing a rich context for further exploration of the topic.

This expanded outline provides a more detailed exploration of the themes and structure of the thesis, offering a comprehensive understanding of the significance of congratulatory rhetoric in political speech. Let me know if you'd like to dive deeper into any specific sections or concepts!

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